

TREAT-AD

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IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enablement Resource

INPP5D (SHIP1) Protein Structures

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Authors	
Collaborating Authors	Adam Hamdani and Andrew Mesecar
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Affiliations	Purdue University

Proteins Purified: The INPP5D gene is a member of the inositol polyphosphate-5-phosphatase (INPP5) family that encodes proteins called the Src homology 2-containing-inositol-phosphatases (SHIP). The complete, full-length SHIP1 protein contains at least 5-domains that are designated as; 1.) the N-terminal SH2 domain (SH2), 2.) the PH-L, 3.) the inositol phosphatase catalytic domain (Ptase), 4.) the C2 domain and 5.) the C-terminal domain containing PXXP and NPXY motifs (*Figure 1*). Several different SHIP1 expression constructs have been generated that contain different domains of the SHIP1 protein (*Table 1, Figure 1*). Construct 4 that encodes the Phosphatase and C2 domains of SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) has primarily been used for biochemical and crystallographic studies. This Ptase-C2 domain has been routinely produced using a baculovirus expression system. A typical yield of 4 mg of SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein can be obtained from 1L of 2×10^6 SF9 cells/mL infected culture. All other constructs yield roughly the same amount or more protein from 1L of 2×10^6 SF9 cells/mL infected culture. Final purity results of each construct can be found in *Figure 2*.

Biophysical Characterization: The quaternary structure of the SHIP1 protein constructs listed in Table 1 were analyzed by size-exclusion chromatography coupled with multi-angle light scattering (SEC-MALS) and Mass-Photometry (REFEYN, Inc.) Analysis of the results from both approaches indicate that the two SHIP1 protein constructs, Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2, exist as monomers in solution at concentrations ranging from nanomolar (Mass Photometry) to micromolar (SEC-MALS). The SHIP1 protein construct containing four domains, SH2-PH-Ptase-C2, was surprisingly observed to exist as a tightly associated dimer over the low nanomolar (10 to 20 nM) to micromolar concentration range (*Figure 4*.) SEC-MALS analysis

was performed on purified full-length SHIP1, however, while the protein is soluble, the SEC-MALS results indicate the protein tends to form aggregates (*Figure 5*.)

Crystallization and X-ray Structural Analysis: The two domain SHIP1 protein construct, Ptase-C2, was found to crystallize under similar conditions as reported for SHIP1 reported in the Protein Databank (PDB code: 6IBD). Reproducible crystals can be grown from a reservoir solution containing 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M BIS-Tris @pH 7.0.) An X-ray structure of SHIP1 with no ligands bound was determined to 2.1 Å resolution. In addition, the X-ray structure of Magnesium(II)-phosphate bound structure was determined to 1.6 Å (*Figure 6*.) Multiple attempts were made to determine X-ray structures of SHIP1 PTase-C2 bound to designed and synthesized ligands via co-crystallization and co-crystallization approaches to no avail. Strong electron density consistent with a bound ligand was not obtained using the crystallization conditions described for PDB:6IBD. Using a modified version of the crystallization solution that contained 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M HEPES pH 7.0, we were ultimately able to determine a ligand-bound structure (*Figure 6*.)

Future Plans: We will continue to use the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein construct and optimize crystallization conditions to obtain ligand-bound X-ray structures. Additionally, all other SHIP1 constructs (*Table 1*) will be subjected to sparse-matrix crystallization screens to identify crystallization conditions for both unbound and ligand-bound proteins.

Conclusion: Thus far, we have shown that the SHIP1 constructs in Table 1 can be successfully expressed and purified using a baculovirus expression system. While the full-length SHIP1 construct can be expressed and purified, SEC-MALS analysis indicates the protein is aggregated. Additionally, the SHIP1 four-domain construct, SH2-PH-Ptase-C2, exists as a tightly associated dimer in solution. Lastly, using a modified version of crystallization conditions reported for PDB:6IBD, high-resolution ligand-bound X-ray crystal structures of the Ptase-C2 domain can be obtained.

Methods:

Generation of baculovirus viral stocks for the expression and purification of SHIP1 proteins:

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) Bacmid Generation: A baculovirus transfer vector encoding SHIP1's Phosphatase and C2 (Ptase-C2) domain (*Figure 1*), gifted by Dr. Opher Gileadi, was transposed into Bacmid DNA following Invitrogen's Bac-to-Bac baculovirus expression protocol. All procedures were carried out in a sterile environment around an open flame.

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P0 viral stock generation: Viral stocks were generated using a modified version of Dr. Opher Gileadi's protein production in insect cells protocol. All procedures were carried out in a BSL2 grade bio-safety cabinet. 1 mL of 4×10^5 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in Gibco SF9 II Serum-Free media were transferred to a sterile 6-well plate. Cell viability was verified using a Bio-Rad automated cell counter. 5 µL (2-3ug) of Bacmid DNA was transferred to 100 µL of Grace's insect medium (GM). 2-4 µL cellfectin II was transferred to 100 µL of GM. Both Bacmid and cellfectin II solutions were mixed and incubated

at room temperature for 45 minutes. Cellfectin II without the addition of bacmid DNA served as the negative control and was diluted in 200 μ L of GM. All samples were diluted with an additional 200 μ L of GM and immediately transferred to their corresponding wells. Transfection took place over 96 hours in an incubator set at 27 °C. After transfection had taken place, the P0 viral stock (supernatant) was harvested and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 700 x g to pellet any dead cells. The clarified P0 viral stock was then transferred to a clean 2 mL microcentrifuge tube and stored in the 4 °C for future use.

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P1 viral stock generation: 3 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) were transferred to a sterile 6-well plate. 120 μ L of P0 viral stock and cellfectin II control were transferred to their corresponding wells. P1 viral stock generation took place over 72 hours in an incubator set at 27 °C. After the allotted time, solutions were transferred to sterile 15 mL conical tubes and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 700 x g to pellet any cell debris. The P1 viral stocks (supernatant) were transferred to new, sterile 15 mL conical tubes and stored at 4 °C for future use.

1 mL of Buffer A (Table 2) was added to each well after removing the P1 viral stocks. Cells were resuspended by pipetting up and down with a P1000 and the solutions were transferred to clean 2 mL microcentrifuge tubes. Samples were placed at -80 °C overnight and thawed at room temperature the following day. Cell solutions were centrifuged at 13,000 x g for 10 minutes using a tabletop centrifuge. Protein concentration for soluble and insoluble fractions were determined using Bradford assay. SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression was verified using SDS-PAGE (*Figure 3a.*)

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) P2 viral stock generation: P2 viral stock generation was performed in suspension cultures using 20 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in 125 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. 100 μ L of P1 viral stock was transferred to its corresponding suspension culture and incubated in a floor incubator set at 27 °C and 120 rpm (*Figure 3b.*) After a 72 hour incubation period, solutions were transferred to sterile 50 mL conical tubes and centrifuged for 15 minutes at 700 x g to pellet the cells. The P2 viral stocks (supernatant) were transferred to new, sterile 50 mL conical tubes and stored at 4 °C for future use.

5 mL of Buffer A was added to each tube containing pelleted P2 viral stocks cells. Cells were resuspended using a serological pipet. Samples were placed at -80 °C overnight and thawed at room temperature the following day. Cell solutions were centrifuged at 25,000 rpm using a floor centrifuge for 30 minutes. Protein concentration for soluble and insoluble fractions were determined using Bradford assay. SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression was verified using SDS-PAGE (*Figure 3b.*)

SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) Large Scale Expression: SHIP1 Ptase-C2 large scale expression was performed using 500 mL of 2×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in 2000 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. 1 mL of P2 viral stock was transferred to each large-scale suspension culture. Infection took place over 72 hours in a floor incubator set at 27 °C with shaking at 120 rpm. After the 72 hr period, cell count, morphology, and viability were checked to verify whether infection had taken place. Proper infection is observed by a reduction in cell doubling time, swollen cells, and a cell

viability between 80-90%. Cells were transferred to 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged for 30 minutes at 700 x g. 120 mL of Buffer A was used to resuspend 1L of infected cells. Cell solutions were transferred to clean, sterile 50 mL conical tubes and placed at -80 °C for future use.

SHIP1 Genscript P2 viral stocks and expression: P2 viral stocks for the remaining constructs were generated by Genscript (Piscataway, NJ.) Expression of SHIP1 constructs PH-Ptase-C2 and SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 (*Figure 1*) were performed in 2L Erlenmeyer flasks containing 500 mL of 2X10⁶ SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%). The volume of P2 viral stock was adjusted so that all cultures were infected with enough virus to equal 0.1 multiplicity of infection (M.O.I.) Viral infection took place over the course of 72 hours in a floor shaker set at 27 °C with shaking at 120 rpm. Cell count, morphology, and viability were checked to verify infection had taken place over the allotted time period. Cultures were transferred to 1L centrifuge bottles and centrifuged at 700 x g for 30 minutes. Cell media was decanted into a solution of 10% bleach and alconox. Cell solutions were resuspended in 120 mL Buffer A and placed into the -80 °C for future use.

SHIP1 Clarified Cell Lysate: All SHIP1 constructs were purified using similar buffers and purification methods. Purification buffers can be found in Table 2. In general, cell solutions were thawed at room temperature and shaken until a slushy consistency was obtained. The solutions were then sonicated on ice using a Branson Sonifier for 3 minutes at 50% amplitude for 6 seconds on and 9 seconds off. A clarified cell lysate was obtained after sonication by centrifuging the cell solution for 30-45 minutes at 25,000 rpm and 4 °C. Samples were then passed through a 0.45 µm filter before proceeding with IMAC.

Immobilized Metal Affinity Chromatography (IMAC) Batch Purification: Clarified cell lysates were incubated with 2-3 mL of HisPur™ Ni-NTA resin (Thermo Scientific) for 1-2 hours at 4 °C in a 250 mL container. The solutions were then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 400 x g to pellet the Nickel resin. The supernatant was decanted into a separate container (flow-through) and the resin was resuspended in 10-15 mL of buffer A. This process was performed several times until the supernatant was clear. The Nickel resin solution was transferred to a gravity filtration column at 4 °C and the remaining buffer A solution was allowed to flow-through until a small amount of liquid remained in the column. The column was washed with a solution containing 90% buffer A and 10% buffer B (*Table 2*) several times. All contents were collected in a clean 50 mL conical tube (wash.) SHIP1 protein was eluted from the Nickel resin using 10-30 mL of 100% buffer B. Protein concentration and purity were determined using the Bradford assay and SDS-PAGE analysis. Fractions that contained SHIP1 were pooled together and 0.5-1 mg of Tobacco-etch virus (TEV) protease was added to the pooled protein. The SHIP1-TEV protein mixture was then placed into dialysis (TEV) overnight at 4 °C to facilitate removal of the N-terminal His-tag and excess imidazole.

After overnight dialysis, the protein sample was incubated with 1-2 mL of nickel resin for 15 minutes and then transferred to a clean gravity column. The solution was allowed to flow through the column and the solution was collected in a clean 50 mL conical tube. The nickel resin was rinsed with 5-10 mL of buffer A. The remaining protein bound to the nickel resin was

eluted using 20 mL of 100% Buffer B. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and the presence of SHIP1 in the determined using SDS-PAGE.

IMAC FPLC Purification: Clarified cell lysates were run on an AKTA pure FPLC attached to a 5 mL Ni-HiTrap HP column (GE Healthcare.) After the lysate was fully loaded, the column was rinsed with buffer A until the absorbance at 280 nm returned to baseline. Samples were then washed with 10% Buffer B to remove any non-specific binders to the Nickel resin. SHIP1 protein was eluted using a 0-100% linear gradient of buffer A to B over 15 minutes at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min. Protein concentration, purity, and removal of the N-terminal His-tag were facilitated using previously described methods (IMAC Batch Binding.)

After overnight dialysis, the protein solution was reloaded onto the 5 mL His-trap column. Flowthrough was collected in 12 mL fractions using the fraction collector. Remaining protein bound to the 5 mL His-trap column was removed with 100% buffer B. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and the presence and purity of SHIP1 in the flowthrough was verified using SDS-PAGE.

SHIP1 Storage and Additional Purification: After isolating SHIP1 protein using IMAC chromatography, samples were concentrated, and buffer exchanged into buffer E (Table 2.) The samples were then flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for future use. If the SHIP1 sample was judged to be <85% pure, an additional purification step was added that involved either strong anion-exchange or gel-filtration chromatography. Note that anion exchange chromatography were only performed on the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2 protein constructs. The SHIP1 SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 four-domain construct does not remain soluble in salt concentrations required for anion-exchange.

Anion Exchange Chromatography (MonoQ): Anion exchange chromatography was performed on SHIP1 constructs Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2 if the desired purity (>90% pure) was not obtained after IMAC chromatography. Protein solutions were placed into anion exchange dialysis buffer (Table 2) to lower the conductivity of the solutions to 2-4 ms/cm. Protein solutions were then loaded onto an 8 mL MonoQTM 10/100 column (Cytiva.) After all of the solution was loaded, protein elution occurred over 2-3 hours using a gradient of 0-50% buffer C to D at a flow rate of 2 mL/min. Protein concentration was determined using Bradford assay and purity of SHIP1 was verified using SDS-PAGE.

Gel Filtration Chromatography: Gel filtration chromatography was performed on all samples prior to any biophysical analysis. Protein solutions were concentrated to 1-2.5 mL and loaded onto a 24 mL Superdex 200 Increase 10/300 GL column (Cytiva.) Depending on the biophysical analysis, the column was equilibrated with a buffer listed in *Table 2*. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3 and the extinction coefficient generated for each SHIP1 protein sequence using ExPASy's ProtParam online calculation tool.

Biophysical Assays:

Size-Exclusion Chromatography coupled with Multi-Angle light scattering (SEC-MALS): SEC-MALS was utilized to determine the molecular weight (M.W.) and oligomeric state of SHIP1 constructs in solution at micromolar concentrations. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3. Protein samples were loaded as 100 μ L volumes and separated using a SRT SEC-300 column (Sepax) in SEC-MALS buffer (Table 2.) SEC-MALS was performed at 4 °C with a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. ASTRA software was used to calculate the molecular weight of each SHIP1 construct.

Mass Photometry Analysis: Mass-photometry was utilized to calculate the M.W. and oligomeric states of SHIP1 constructs in solution at nM concentrations. Protein concentrations were determined using a Biotek Take3. SHIP1 protein solutions at a concentration of 100 nM were prepared in REFEYN buffer (Table 2.) All analyses took place on a clean coverslip containing a rubber gasket. 15 μ L of Refeyn buffer was added to the rubber gasket well and the Mass-photometry lens was focused. 3 μ L of the 100nM SHIP1 protein solution was added to the drop and mixed using a pipette. Data was collected over 1 minute. The molecular weight of SHIP1 proteins were calculated using a calibration curve made with proteins of known molecular weight.

Crystallization and X-ray data collection: The SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein construct was crystallized using a previously established crystal condition (PDB – 6IBD, 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M BIS-Tris pH 7.0.) Protein crystallization was performed in 24-well sitting drop plates by preparing drops (final volume of 3 μ L) as a 1:1 ratio of protein to reservoir solution. Crystals were allowed to grow for at least 1 week at room temperature. Crystals with sizes amenable for X-ray data collection were then cryoprotected with 2.5 μ L of cryosolution (90% reservoir solution + 10% PEG 400.) Crystals were harvested with nylon loops and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen. X-ray data collection was performed at the LS-CAT beamline at the Advanced Photon Source, Argonne National Laboratory. Several high-resolution datasets (1.4-2.1 Å) were obtained. Crystals of SHIP1-ligand complexes were prepared using similar methods described above, except SHIP1 was pre-incubated with inhibitor at 10-times the determined IC₅₀ value for at least 4 hours. In addition, the crystallization solutions were optimized and ligand-bound SHIP1 structures resulted using 17-22% PEG 2000MME, 7-10% PEG 3000, 0.1M HEPES @ pH 7.0 as the crystallization solution. Ligand density was identified using difference Fo-Fc difference electron density maps and the X-ray structure of SHIP1 (PDB:6IBD) that had all of the waters and ligands removed from the coordinate file.

Figure 1. Four SHIP1 constructs (1 thru 4) were designed for biochemical, biophysical and X-ray structure analysis. These constructs were designed based on the primary sequence of SHIP1 deposited into uniprot and using protein primary sequence homology. All constructs were designed and codon-optimized for baculovirus expression. P2 viral stocks of each construct were generated by Genscript, except for construct 4 (Ptase-C2). The baculovirus expression plasmid for the SHIP1 Ptase-C2 protein was a generous gift from Dr. Opher Gileadi (University of Oxford).

Table 1		
Construct	Protein Sequence	M.W.
Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence before Tag removal	MGHHHHHHSSMSPILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLEYLEEKYEEHLY ERDEGDKWRNKKFELGLEFPNLPYYIDGDVCLTQSMAIRYIAD KHNMLGGCPKERAEISMLEGAVLDIRYGVSR IAYS KDFETLKVD FLSKLPEMLKMFEDRLCHKTYLNGDHVTHPDFMLYDALDVVL YMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKKRIEAI PQIDKYLKSSKYIAWPLQGWQ ATFGGGDHPPKSSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMEQPEPDMITIFIGTWN MGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLS EKEWLEILKHSLQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRIS HICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGV SFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSE KKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLS PFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNRY VDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFLHFEEE EITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKS YPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPG TVDSQGQIEFLRCYATLKTQS QTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGEN EEGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLP IISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESY GEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ	81077.3 9
Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence after Tag removal	SMEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDS ADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHSLQEITSVTFKTVAIHT LWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGV SF MFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLS P FNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSH DQLLTERREQKVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKA TGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKS YPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPV FATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGQIEFLRCYATLKTQS QTKF YLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENEEGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLP IISDP EYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESY GEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ	52812.7 9
PH-Ptase-C2 Protein Sequence before Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKM QLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGSEDKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVI LVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPD MITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIY VIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHSLQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVL AKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGV SFMFNGTSLGF VNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLS PFNITHRFTH LFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTER REQKVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPS WCDRVLWKS YPLVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGV	67327.7 1

	TSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGQIEFLRCYATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLE ESFVKSQEGENESEGELVVKFGETLPKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHIL ISIKSSDSDES YGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQG EIKLQTSQG	
PH- Ptase- C2 Protein Sequenc e after Tag removal	SNRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGSE DKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVLVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKK REGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKKITS WFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHS LQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIA NTLGNKGAVGV SFMNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMN ILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETII QKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFHLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFER LTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQS YGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGQIEFL RCYATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENESEGELVVK FGETLPKPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDES YGEGCIALRLE ATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQG	65036.2 2
SH2- PH- Ptase- C2 Protein Sequenc e before Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNVPCWNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTG KDGSFLVRASESISRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQA SEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKNMGLVTHLQYVPVLEEEDTGDD PEEDTVESVVSPPPELPPRNIPLTASSCEAKEVPFSNENPRATETSR PSLSETLFRQLQSMDSGLPEEHLKAIQDYLSTQLAQDSEFVKTG SSSLPHLKKLTLLCKELYGEVIRTLPSLESLQRLFDQQLSPGLRP RPQVPGEANPINMVSKLSQLTSLSSIEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRP SLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGSEDFK YSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVLVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREG FCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKKITSWFL SKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHS LQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIAN TLGNKGAVGV SFMNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILR FLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNRYVDLPTWEAETIIQKI KQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFHLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERL TRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQSYGS TSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGQIEFLRCY ATLKTKSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENESEGELVVKFGE	99802.3 9

	<p>TLPKLPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQG</p>	
<p>SH2- PH- Ptase- C2</p> <p>Protein Sequenc e after Tag removal</p>	<p>SNVPCWNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDGSFLVRASESISRAYALC VLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYK KENMGLVTHLQYPVPLEEEDTGDDPEEDTVESVVSPPELPPRNIP LTASSCEAKEVPFSNENPRATETSRLSLSETLFQRLQSMDTSGLPE EHLKAIQDYLSTQLAQDSEFVKTGSSSLPHLKKLTLLCKELYGE VIRTLPSLESLQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVPGEANPINMVSKLSQLT SLLSSIEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQ LKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGEDKIFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKLVL VETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMI TIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDYVI GTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHSLEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAK PEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAVGVSFMFNGTSLGFVN SHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLF WFGDLNYRVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQ KVFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSW CDRVLWKSYPVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQ FVSKNGPGTVDSQGQIEFLRCYATLKTQSQTKFYLEFHSSCLESF VKSQEGENESEGELVVKFGETLPKLPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIK SSDSDESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKL QTSQG</p>	<p>97510.9</p>

Full- Length Protein Sequenc e before Tag removal	SNNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDG SFLVRASESISRAYALCVLYRN CVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVSMRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKENMG LVTHLQYPVPLEEEDTGDDPEEDTVESVVSPPELPPRNIPLTASSC EAKEVPFSNENPRATETSRPSLSETLFQRLQSMDSGLPEEHLKAI QDYLSTQLAQDSEFVKTGSSSLPHLKKLTLLCKELYGEVIRTLP SLESLQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVPGEANPINMVSKLSQLTSLSSI EDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPVTFEVKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDV ESGKLIKKSKDGSEDKFYSHKKILQLIKSQKFLNKL VILVETEKE KILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQQMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGT WNMGNAPPPKKITSWFLSKGQGKTRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQED PLSEKEWLEILKHS LQEITSVTFKTVAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHEN RISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGA VGV SFMFGTSLGFVNSHLTS GSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDKKLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDL NYRVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYADLLSHDQLLTERREQKVFLH FEEEEITFAPTYR FERL TRDKYAYTKQKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVL WKSYP LVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSDHSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKN GPGTVDSQGQIEFLRCYATLKTQS QTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQE GENEEGSEGELVVKFGETLPKLPKPIISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSD ESYGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPLTHHGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQ GKTREKLYDFVKTERDESSGPKTLKSLTSHDPMKQWEVTSRAPP CSGSSITEIINPNYMGVGPFGPPMPLHVKQTLSPDQQPTAWSYDQ PPKDSPLGPCRGESPTPPGQPPISP K KFLPSTANRGLPPRTQESRP SDLGKNAGDTLPQEDLPLTKPEMFENPLYGSLSSF PKPAPRKDQ ESPKMPRKEPPPCPEPGILSPSIVLTKAQEADRGE GPGKQVPAPRL RSFTCSSSAEGRAAGGDKSQGKPKTPVSSQAPVPAKRPIKPSRSEI NQQTPTPTPRPPLPVKSPAVLHLQH SKGRDYRDNTELP HHGKH RPEEGPPGPLGRTAMQ	135168. 36
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Full- Length Protein Sequenc e after Tag removal	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQSNHGNITRSKAEELLSRTGKDGS FLVRASESISRAYALCVLYRNCVYTYRILPNEDDKFTVQASEGVS MRFFTKLDQLIEFYKKENMGLVTHLQYVPLEEDTGDDPEEDT VESVVSPELPPRNIPLTASSCEAKEVPFSNENPRATETSRPSLSET LFQRLQSMDTSGLP EEHLKAIQDY LSTQLAQDSEFVKTGSSSLPH LKKLTTLLCKELYGEVIRTLPSLES LQRLFDQQLSPGLRPRPQVP GEANPINMVS KLSQLT SLLSSIEDKVKALLHEGPESPHRPSLIPPV TFE VKAESLGIPQKMQLKVDVESGKLIKKSKDGS EDKIFYSHKKI LQLIKSQKFLNKL VILVETEKEKILRKEYVFADSKKREGFCQLLQ QMKNKHSEQPEPDMITIFIGTWNMGNAPPPKITSWFLSKGQ GK TRDDSADYIPHDIYVIGTQEDPLSEKEWLEILKHS LQEITSVTFKT VAIHTLWNIRIVVLAKPEHENRISHICTDNVKTGIANTLGNKGAV GVSFMFNGTSLGFVNSHLTSGSEKKLRRNQNYMNILRFLALGDK KLSPFNITHRFTHLFWFGDLNYRVDLPTWEAETIIQKIKQQQYAD LLSHDQLLTERREQK VFLHFEEEEITFAPTYRFERLTRDKYAYTK QKATGMKYNLPSWCDRVLWKSYP LVHVVCQSYGSTSDIMTSD HSPVFATFEAGVTSQFVSKNGPGTVDSQGGQIEFLRCYATLKT KS QTKFYLEFHSSCLESFVKSQEGENE EGSEGELVVKFGETLPK LKP IISDPEYLLDQHILISIKSSDSDES YGEGCIALRLEATETQLPIYTPL THGELTGHFQGEIKLQTSQGKTREKLYDFVKTERDESSGPKTL KSLTSHDPMKQWEVTSRAPP CSGSSITEINPNYMGVGPFGPPMP LHVKQTLSPDQQPTAWSYDQPPKDSPLGCRGES PPTPPGQPPIS PKKFLPSTANRGLPPRTQESRPSDLGKNAGDTLPQEDLPLTKPEM FENPLYGSLSSFPKPAPRKDQESPKMPRKEPPPCPEPGILSPSIVLT KAQEADRGE GPGKQVPAPRLRSFTCSSSAEGRAAGGDKSQGKP KTPVSSQAPVPAKRPIKPSRSEINQQT PPTPTPRPPLPVKSPAVLH LQHSKGRDYRDNTELP HHGKHRPEEGPPGPLGRTAMQ	135168. 36
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Table 2			
<i>Purification</i>	<i>Buffer</i>	<i>Components</i>	<i>pH</i>
Ptase-C2 and PH-Ptase-C2	A (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol	8
	B (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 400mM Imidazole, 5% Glycerol	8
	C (Anion Exchange)	20mM Tris-Base	8
	D (Anion Exchange)	50mM Tris-Base, 1M NaCl	8
	E (Sizing/Storage)	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	Dialysis (TEV)	50mM Tris-Base, 250mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 5mM B-ME	8
	Dialysis (Anion Exchange)	20mM Tris-Base	8
SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 and Full-Length	A (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol	8
	B (HiTrap)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 400mM Imidazole, 5% Glycerol	8
	F (Storage)	50mM HEPES, 500mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	Dialysis (TEV)	50mM Tris-Base, 500mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 5mM B-ME	8
N/A	Crystallization/DSF	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% Glycerol	7.5
	CryoEM/Refyne/SE C-MAL	50mM HEPES, 250mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP	7.5
	Phosphatase Assay	50mM HEPES, 150mM NaCl, 2mM MgCl ₂	7.4

Figure 2. SHIP1 constructs were purified using several different multi-step purification strategies including IMAC, anion-exchange, and gel-filtration chromatography. The purity of each construct was analyzed using SDS-PAGE (10% gels). Approximately 2ug of protein as loaded into each lane. **A.** SDS-PAGE analysis after the final purification step for SHIP1 protein constructs Ptase-C2 (lane 2), PH-Ptase-C2 (lane 3), SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 (lane 4). **B.** SDS-PAGE analysis of purification of full-length SHIP1 (Lane 2). Molecular weight standard are shown in lane 1 for each gel and are given in kDa.

Figure 3. Generation of P1 and P2 viral stocks encoding SHIP1's Ptase-C2 domain. **A.** 120 μ L of P0 viral stock was used to infect 3 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in sterile 6-well plates. The plates were incubated for a total of 72 hours in an incubator set at 27 $^{\circ}$ C. SDS-PAGE analysis was used to verify SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression in the soluble and insoluble fractions. A P0 "viral stock" generated using only cellfectin II and no Bacmid DNA served as the positive control. **B.** 100 μ L of P1 viral stock was used to infect 20 mL of 1×10^6 SF9 II cell/mL (viability >95%) in 125 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. Suspension cultures were incubated in a floor incubator set at 27 $^{\circ}$ C and shaking at 120 rpm. SDS-PAGE analysis was used to verify SHIP1 Ptase-C2 expression in the soluble and insoluble fractions. A P0 "viral stock" generated using only cellfectin II and no Bacmid DNA served as the positive control.

Figure 4. Quaternary structure analysis of SHIP1 protein constructs Ptase-C2, PH-Ptase-C2, and SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 using SEC-MALS and mass photometry. Please refer to *Table 1* for the predicted molecular weights. **A.** SEC-MALS results obtained from this experiment indicate that SHIP1 construct SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 exists as a dimer in solution at micromolar concentrations **B.** mass photometry (REFEYN, Inc.) results obtained from this experiment indicate that SHIP1 construct SH2-PH-Ptase-C2 exists as a dimer in solution as low as 10 to 20 nM concentration.

Mw (kDa)	Polydispersity (Mw/Mn)	r(avg) (nm)	Calculated mass (μg)
122758.2	1.662	73.1	4.78
(5.90%)	(6.32%)	(0.00%)	(100%)

Figure 5. SEC-MALS analysis of the purified, full-length SHIP1 protein. Results indicate the protein is highly aggregated.

Figure 6. X-ray structures of three SHIP1 (Ptase-C2) crystallized with different ligands and under slightly different conditions. **A.** Unbound SHIP1 structure determined to 2.1 Å. The phosphatase domain is colored in red and the C2 domain is colored in green. A glycerol molecule was modeled in between the Ptase and C2 domains. **B.** A magnesium (II) and phosphate bound structure of SHIP1 was determined to 1.6 Å. Both magnesium and phosphate can be found bound within the active site of the phosphatase domain. **C.** X-ray structure of SHIP1 Ptase-C3 modified with a covalent inhibitor determined to 1.8 Å. The molecule was found to be covalently bound to Cysteine 504 which is between the Ptase and C2 domains.

INPP5D Construct	K _m (μM)	k _{cat} (s ⁻¹)	k _{cat} /K _m (s ⁻¹ M ⁻¹)	n _H (Hi II)	Predicted Molecular Weight	Determined Quaternary Structure
Ptase	42.7 ± 8.3	1.36 ± 0.18	(3.19 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵			
Ptase+C2	25.1 ± 0.9	4.2 ± 0.1	(1.68 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵	2.1 ± 0.1	53 kDa	Monomer (SEC-MALS)
PH+Ptase+C2	23.5 ± 0.7	3.8 ± 0.1	(1.63 ± 0.05) × 10 ⁵	2.3 ± 0.1	65 kDa	Monomer (SEC-MALS)
SH2+PH+Ptase+C2	26.7 ± 1.2	3.3 ± 0.1	(1.24 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁵	2.1 ± 0.2	98 kDa	Dimer (SEC-MALS)
Full Length	37.0 ± 2.4	1.06 ± 0.03	(0.29 ± 0.02) × 10 ⁵	1.7 ± 0.1	133 kDa	